

Researches on Multidisciplinary Approaches

Multidisipliner Akademik Yaklaşım Araştırmaları 2023, 3(1): 147-154

Features And Prospects Of Tourism Development In The World And In Kazakhstan

Derleme Makale

Mustafayeva Bagila / akademik derecesi

Hoca Ahmed Yesevi adını taşıyan Uluslararası Kazak-Türk Üniversitesi, Yönetim Ekonomisi ve Hukuk fakültesi, Ekonomi, Finans ve Muhasebe Bölümü, bagikaz@mail.ru

Abstract

The modern tourism industry is one of the largest sectors of the world economy. It's a pretty big income for both the business and the country as a whole. In many countries of the world, tourism is developing as a system that provides all opportunities to get acquainted with the history, culture, traditions, spiritual and religious values of a particular country and its people and generates income for the treasury. causing small businesses to disappear. Purpose of the study: to analyze and find out what affects world tourism in general and what can help maintain the status of world tourism until the pandemic is over for the time being. The significance of this study is that world tourism has a great impact on the economies of countries, as well as on the economic component of individual organizations. Solving the problem of the current state of world tourism will help prevent an economic crisis both in Kazakhstan and in other countries. Some of the main tasks of this study will be: To examine the structure of world tourism and what it includes. Analyzes how world tourism affects the economic components and tourism organizations of countries. Identifies solutions that will contribute to the development of tourism. Currently, international tourism has an impact on both political and economic relations in the world community. Tourism contributes to the change of the country's economy. This also applies to the development of international tourism.

Keywords: Tourism, History, Culture, Customs, Tourism Market.

Jel Codes: Z3, Z32

Dünyada ve Kazakistan'da Turizmin Gelişiminin Özellikleri ve Beklentileri

Özet

Modern turizm endüstrisi, dünya ekonomisinin en büyük sektörlerinden biridir. Hem işletme hem de bir bütün olarak ülke için oldukça büyük bir gelir. Dünyanın birçok ülkesinde turizm, belirli bir ülkenin ve halkının tarihini, kültürünü, geleneklerini, manevi ve dini değerlerini tanımak için tüm olanakları sağlayan ve hazineye gelir sağlayan bir sistem olarak gelişmektedir. Ancak pandeminin istikrarsız durumu nedeniyle sektör büyük kayıplar yaşıyor, bu da turizm ve çeşitlilikte küçük işletmelerin yok olmasına neden oluyor. Çalışmanın amacı: genel olarak dünya turizmini neyin etkilediğini ve pandemi şu an için kapanana kadar dünya turizminin durumunu korumaya neyin yardımcı olabileceğini analiz etmek ve bulmak. Bu çalışmanın önemi, dünya turizminin ülkelerin ekonomileri ve ayrıca bireysel organizasyonların ekonomik bileşeni üzerinde büyük bir etkiye sahip olmasıdır. Şu anda dünya turizminin durumu sorununu çözmek, hem Kazakistan'da hem de diğer ülkelerde ekonomik bir krizin önlenmesine yardımcı olacaktır. Bu çalışmanın ana görevlerinden bazıları şunlar olacaktır: Dünya turizminin yapısını ve neleri içerdiğini incelemek. Dünya turizminin ülkelerin ekonomik bileşenlerini ve turizm organizasyonlarını nasıl etkilediğini analiz eder. Turizmin gelişmesine katkı sağlayacak çözümleri belirler. Şu anda uluslararası turizm, dünya toplumundaki hem siyasi hem de ekonomik ilişkiler üzerinde bir etkiye sahiptir. Turizm ülke ekonomisinin değişmesine katkıda bulunur. Bu aynı zamanda uluslararası turizmin gelişimi için de geçerlidir.

Anahatar Kelimeler: Turizm, Tarih, Kültür, Gelenekler, Turizm Pazarı.

Jel Kodu: Z3, Z32

Introduction

Currently, the tourism industry in many countries of the world is one of the leading branches of the national economy. It accounts for about 10% of the world's gross domestic product, taking into account all jobs and global consumer spending. In addition, the constant emergence of new types of tourism gradually contributes to the increasing growth of the industry. Today, for the development of cultural and historical tourism, first of all, it is necessary to attract investors, search for internal reserves and regulate legislation on tourism in order to modernize and repair the infrastructure of territories with historical ancient cities, their monuments, buildings, etc. In order to develop the urban environment, it is also advisable to form a management system within the historical zone, creating a special fund for cultural and historical tourism. The transformation of ancient cities into tourist centers will contribute to the development of tourism at the national and international levels, in the future, to make tourism one of the most profitable sectors of the economy.

Conceptual Framework

Uneven distribution of international tourist flows in different regions and countries is one of the features of modern tourism development. At the same time, 20-30% of the total person's numbers traveling abroad are mass, or group, tourists, and the remaining 70-80% are individual tourists traveling mainly to neighboring areas.

In recent years, there is a predominance of mass tourism, which is a consequence of the following factors:

- an increase in free time;
- reduction in the price of air travel;
- an increase in the number of charter flights for the convenience of tourists traveling in groups;
- increasing interest of tour operators to mass tourism as a business, which gives considerable profit;
- searching for new economically profitable directions;
- increasing the number of jobs in mass tourism;
- an increase in the number of tourists traveling by bus due to the low price of the tour package.

The following is noted in the trends of mass tourism development: individual tourism (tourists who travel independently with tourist purposes) grows slower than mass tourism (Kazybaikyzy A., Mukhanova A.E., Smagulova ZhB, 2015: No. 1-2. 265-269).

Although tourists who plan vacations individually have some advantages, but it is quite difficult to realize such long-distance trips because of the high cost of individual programs.

The volume of travel for recreational purposes is increasing compared to the volume of business tourism. For example, if in the 1970s the business segment prevailed at the international tourism market, then now the ratio has not changed in favor of recreational tourism: 60% of tourists travel for leisure and only 40% for business travel.

In all economically developed countries, workers receive paid leave, and its duration is also increasing. In Japan, for example, employees in many categories have 7 weeks of vacation a year, which allows them to travel for long periods of time. Customer demands for service are also growing. This manifests itself in the fact that tourists are increasingly traveling, recognizing

modern service and demanding greater comfort. There is an increase in mobility of the population. Having your own car makes it possible to travel safely. The costs of tourists during their travels are increasing (Ovcharov, A. O, 2021:253).

Tour operators are experiencing strong competition from airlines, which have begun to sell their own tours, combining the air ticket with the services of direct suppliers of tour services (hotels, excursion bureaus, etc.). The importance of psychological factors has increased. In order to work successfully in the tourism business it is necessary to learn how to reach an emotional contact with customers. The hospitality industry requires friendly workers.

Each company, city, region and even country has its own image and reputation. For example, Italy is the land of spaghetti, Finland is the home of Santa Claus and Paris is the city of love. Creating an image is a long and consistent process.

At the end of the XX century there were significant changes on the international tourism market, new fashionable tourist regions emerged and the competition intensified in this regard. Such new tourist regions include the South-East Asia edges: Vietnam, Cambodia, Laos and some former republics of the Soviet Union; in Latin America - Chile; in Africa - South Africa. Even Japan, once considered a tourist-generating country, is beginning to attract more and more attention, and the tourist flow is now heading not only from Japan but also to Japan.

Some tourist regions provide a fairly high standard of service. The leaders of many countries are seriously involved in tourism development programs; serious investments are made to create amusement parks, new attractions and trendy attractions.

- In the first period of the XXI century the world tourism industry faced the problem of conservation and development of recreational resources, which are a priceless gift of nature, requiring a careful attitude, so that in the third millennium mankind was able to use this gift. To maximize the use of recreational resources it is necessary to achieve a ratio between the increased demand for these resources and the creation of the most favorable conditions for their use (Lee, D., Hampton, M., Jeyacheya, J. 2014: 194-223; Scott, D., Gössling, S., Hall, C., Peeters, P. 2015: 1-21).
- In the coming years, the tourism markets of developed industrialized countries will grow steadily due to the increasing accessibility of tourism to wider segments of the population and the increasing frequency of tourist trips. New and developing tourism markets are characterized by continuing dynamic growth and a corresponding increase in budget revenues. A gradual shift in tourism development from the traditional markets of Western Europe, the USA, Japan and Canada to alternative markets such as Central and Eastern Europe (including Russia), China, South Korea, Mexico and some Middle Eastern countries is expected (see table 1) (Cardenas-Garcia, P., Sanchez-Rivero, M., Pulido-Fernandez, J. 2013: 206-221; Wang, J.Y.; Zhang, H. 2019:62–68; Zhou, Q.L.; Zhan, B.M. 2017: 111–124).

Table 1: Forecast distribution of inbound tourism by world regions (international tourist arrivals, million people)

World regions	Arrivals					
	1985	1990	1995	2000	2010	2023 (forecast)
Total	327,1	457,2	565,4	667,7	1006,4	1561,1
Africa	9,7	15,0	20,2	27,4	47,0	77,3
Americas (North and South)	65,3	92,8	108,9	130,2	190,4	282,3
East Asia (Pacific)	31,1	54,6	81,4	92,9	195,2	397,2
Europe	212,0	282,7	338,4	393,4	527,3	717,0
Middle East	7,5	9,0	12,4	18,3	25,9	68,5
South Asia	2,5	3,2	4,2	5,5	10,6	18,8

References: Committee on Statistics of the Republic of Kazakhstan. URL: <http://stat.gov.kz>

Method

The modern tourism industry is one of the largest highly profitable and dynamically developing segments of international trade in services. Tourism accounts for about 10% of the world's total product, 30% of the world's service exports, 7% of the world's investment, 10% of the world's jobs and 5% of all tax revenues. Taking into consideration the rapid and uninterrupted growth of tourism which continued during the last decade, as well as its considerable influence on the economy and society wellbeing, developed and developing countries determined tourism industry as one of the economic priorities. In Kazakhstan, investment in tourism has reached a record high in the country history - 153.7 billion tenge.

The industry is developing at a moderate pace with a small socio-economic effect on a national scale. In 2019, the cumulative contribution of tourism by WTTC methodology to total GDP was 5.6%.

In this case, by 2025 it is planned to increase the contribution of tourism in the economy to 8%. That is, investment in the tourism industry and the expenditure of domestic and foreign tourists should grow by an average of 7-8% per year. As statistics shows, if the current dynamics of the industry development is maintained, the indicator will be achieved ahead of schedule (Liu, G.B. 2019: 128; Ke, S.Z.; Han, F. 2013: 64–71).

Thus, over the last ten years the average annual growth of investment in fixed capital in the sphere of art, entertainment and recreation was at the level of 10%, and at the end of 2019 the growth of investment reached 46.2% for the year. In monetary terms, the volume of capital investments in 2019 amounted to 153.7 billion tenge, setting a new record in the country's history. At the same time, the contribution of the state in financing the sphere was 40.2%, the share of own capital - 46.2%, and the remaining 13.6% - bank loans and borrowed funds.

Every third Kazakhstani tourist chooses to vacation within the country. According to the results of nine months of 2019, 8.2 million Kazakhstanis visited foreign countries as tourists. Compared with the same period of 2018, the indicator slightly decreased - by 0.1%. Domestic tourism, on the contrary, increased immediately by 9.8% to 5.1 million people. That is, every third Kazakh tourist in 2019 rested inside the country. In turn, the tourist flow from abroad to Kazakhstan after the International Exhibition "EXPO-2017" crossed the limit of 6 million tourists a year. As a result, 6.4 million foreign tourists visited Kazakhstan in the first nine months of 2019. Compared to the same period of 2018, the indicator decreased by 5.4%, but, nevertheless, it remained above the annual average for the last five years by 650 thousand tourists.

Findings and Interpretation

Kazakhstan is mostly visited by citizens of Russia, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, China, Germany, Ukraine, Turkey, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and India. Tourists spent 92.1 billion tenge on accommodation in Kazakhstan. In Kazakhstan there are 3.6 thousand places of accommodation for tourists: hotels (2.1 thousand units), small houses and apartments (1.1 thousand), children's camps (120), specialized holiday homes (84), tourist centers (53) and other types of accommodation. Half of all accommodations are concentrated in the East Kazakhstan (567 units), Almaty (540), Akmola (407) regions and Almaty (341).

According to the results of nine months of 2019, 4.9 million tourists, including Kazakhstani tourists used accommodation services. At that, about 60% of tourists stayed in Almaty (984.7 thousand people), Almaty region (733.7 thousand), Astana (654.1 thousand) and East-Kazakhstan region (484.8 thousand). The volume of accommodation services rendered to them in aggregate reached 92.1 billion tenge. Compared with the same period of 2018, the indicator increased by 16.6% (Plan for the development of the tourism industry in the Republic of Kazakhstan: Order of the Minister for Investment and Development No. 256 dated December 9, 2014).

It is noteworthy that the average annual occupancy rate of accommodations has remained practically unchanged over the past five years and ranges from 22% to 25%. At the same time, the number of tourist accommodations grows annually with the intensity of 12.5%. That is, statistics demonstrates the intensive development of regional tourism in the country. However, the reason for the continuing occupancy rate of accommodations lies elsewhere, namely in their uneven distribution according to the tourist flow. Thus, in the resort areas of East Kazakhstan region, leading in the number of accommodations, each accommodation facility served an average of 855 people in the first nine months of 2019. Similarly in Akmola region: one accommodation facility served 762 people. In turn, in Nur-Sultan city, where 208 places of accommodation are concentrated, an average of 3.1 thousand people was served by each facility. In the city of Almaty - 2.9 thousand people, in Mangistau region - 2 thousand people, in Atyrau region - 1.9 thousand people. As a result, this leads to increased wear and tear of accommodation facilities, reduced competition in the regions and deterioration of service quality.

Development of infrastructure of priority destinations will increase the flow of tourists to 15 million people a year

In Kazakhstan, there are more than 100 tourist sites capable of becoming so-called "tourist magnets" and "points of tourist growth. The development of their tourist infrastructure requires significant investment. However, due to limited financial resources, 10 republican destinations and 50 regional destinations were selected, which were included in the Map of Touristification of Kazakhstan (Panova, A.V. :2021. 248).

Thus, the top 10 priority tourist areas of Kazakhstan, presenting high potential for tourism development, include:

1. Lake Alakol with potential of 2.5 million tourists a year (current flow - 772 thousand tourists);
2. Mountain cluster of Almaty region with potential of 2.5 million tourists a year (current flow - 500 thousand tourists);
3. Shchuchinsko-Borovsky resort zone with the potential of 2 million tourists a year (current flow - 750 thousand);
4. Bayanaul resort zone with potential of 450 thousand tourists per year (current flow - 200 thousand);
5. Imantau-Shalkar resort zone with potential of 400 thousand tourists a year (current flow - 130 thousand);
6. Balkhash lake with potential of 400 thousand tourists a year (current flow - 130 thousand);
7. historical and cultural center of Turkestan with the potential of 1.5 million tourists a year (current flow - 500 thousand);
8. beach recreation in Mangistau with the potential of 750 thousand tourists a year;
9. MICE tourism in the city of Nur-Sultan with the potential of 1 million tourists a year;
10. Tourist zone "Baikonur" with the potential from 250 thousand to 500 thousand tourists a year.

That is, the annual flow of tourists, including Kazakh tourists, is expected to increase by more than 6 million people and reach an indicator of 15 million tourists. As a result, the profitability of the industry will increase. For example, the volume of provided services for tourist accommodation will increase by approximately 200 billion tenge. Arrivals of tourists from the UAE, India and Malaysia increased by 50%, 49% and 44%, respectively.

Conclusion and Discussion

The availability of direct flights plays a significant role in increasing the arrival of foreign nationals in Kazakhstan. For example, direct flights from such countries as UAE (Dubai - Almaty, Dubai - Aktau), India (Nur-Sultan - Delhi), Malaysia (Almaty - Kuala Lumpur), which allowed to increase the tourist flow by 50%, 49% and 44% respectively.

Moreover, the main foreign market to attract tourists for Kazakhstan remains Russia, with more than 10 direct destinations available with the regions. The most popular are flights from Tyumen, Krasnodar, Tomsk, Sochi, Moscow, Novosibirsk, St. Petersburg, etc.

Airlines regularly expand international air routes. For example, in 2018, new direct flights were opened: Atyrau - Frankfurt, Nur-Sultan - Vilnius, Nur-Sultan - Dushanbe, Almaty - Riga, Nur-Sultan - Helsinki. And already in 2019, Tajikistan and Germany are among the top 10 countries in terms of tourist inflow to Kazakhstan, increasing tourist flows [8].

The experience of Dubai and Singapore prove that the functioning of an international financial center contributes to the acceleration of tourism industry growth.

Thus, the functioning of the Dubai International Financial Center (DIFC) has increased the attractiveness of the country's tourism by creating a favorable environment for businesses and financial institutions. Providing them with the necessary legal, commercial and other infrastructure ensured accelerated growth of the business sector in the country. As a result, Dubai has attracted the world's largest companies to the country. As of January 2020, about 2.5 thousand

companies are registered in the jurisdiction of Dubai International Financial Center, whose contribution to the GDP of Dubai by 2024 will be about 15% (Ruda, A.; Pokladníková, M. 2016: 67–83; Nestoroska, I. 2012: 95–103; Wang, S.J.; Xie, J.; Yue, Z.L. 2020: 1–10).

The Astana International Financial Center operates in Kazakhstan, in the jurisdiction of which more than 390 companies from 26 countries are registered. According to the results of 2019, MFCA attracted about \$130 million of foreign direct investment. At the same time, the main flow of money came in the oil and gas and chemical industry, agricultural processing, financial services, tourism and education.

Taking into consideration the fact that the current state of tourism sector is hampered by insufficient flows of investment funds, and the country has unique tourist destinations, 11 of which are included in the UNESCO World Cultural Heritage List, the potential of IFCA will accelerate the development of the sphere and raise the international status of the country. How will Kazakhstan benefit from tourism development?

Development of tourism industry contributes to strengthening interstate relations and culture, increasing the inflow of foreign currency, growth of balance of payments, stimulating exports of goods and services, increasing employment, construction and reconstruction of infrastructure facilities, as well as accelerating diversification of economic sectors. As a result, in Kazakhstan about 200 thousand new jobs will be created, including 72 thousand permanent ones, and the net profit of tourist activity for all interested sides - the state, business and workers - will increase to 200 billion tenge a year (at the moment the profitability is about 118 billion tenge) (Program for the development of promising areas of the tourism industry of the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2010-2014. On approval of the State program for the development of the tourism industry of the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2019-2025.).

In conclusion, research conducted by the World Tourism Organization (WTO) shows that the state of the world tourism industry, despite the objective difficulties of recent years, is generally stable and the industry retains the position of the largest, highly profitable and rapidly developing sector of the world economy.

This fact explains the increased interest in the tourism sphere on the part of the governments of most countries with influential structures of executive power to ensure effective state policy for its development.

Thank

We express our gratitude to the library staff of the International Kazakh-Turkish University named after H. A. Yasavi, which allowed us to use the works of domestic and foreign scientists and practitioners, the theory of modern tourism, the city administration apparatus, which allowed us to obtain statistical data necessary for the effective management of materials obtained as a result of the author's analysis.

Source

Cardenas-Garcia, P., Sanchez-Rivero, M., Pulido-Fernandez, J. (2013). Does tourism growth influence economic development? *Journal of Travel Research*, 54(2), 206-221.

Committee on Statistics of the Republic of Kazakhstan. URL: <http://stat.gov.kz>.

- Kazybaikyzy A., Mukhanova A.E., Smagulova Zh.B (2015). Features And Prospects Of Development Of Tourism In The World // *Successes of modern natural science*. - No. 1-2. – P. 265-269; URL: <https://natural-sciences.ru/ru/article/view?id=34827> (date of access: 07/01/2022).
- Ke, S.Z.; Han, F. (2013). A composite measure and statistical estimation of China's urban economic development potentials. *Stat. Res.*, 3, 64–71. [Google Scholar]
- Lee, D., Hampton, M., Jeyacheya, J. (2014), The political economy of precarious work in the tourism industry in small island developing states. *Review of International Political Economy*, 22(1), 194-223.
- Liu, G.B. (2019). Research on the advancing path and policy innovation of the Belt and Road Initiative. *Northeast Asia Forum*, 4, 128. [Google Scholar].
- Nestoroska, I. (2012). Identifying tourism potentials in Republic of Macedonia through regional approach. *Procedia-Soc. Behav. Sci.*, 44, 95–103. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef].
- Ovcharov, A. O. (2021). *Economics of tourism: textbook*, Moscow: INFRA-M,- 253 p.
- Panova, A.V. (2021). *Tourism statistics: textbook*, Moscow: INFRA-M, - 248 p.
- Plan for the development of the tourism industry in the Republic of Kazakhstan: Order of the Minister for Investment and Development No. 256 dated December 9, 2014.
- Program for the development of promising areas of the tourism industry of the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2010-2014. On approval of the State program for the development of the tourism industry of the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2019-2025.
- Ruda, A.; Pokladníková, M.(2016). Map algebra in tourism potential modelling for improving social issues in Masaryk's school forest enterprise Křtiny. *Geogr. Tech.*, 11, 67–83. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef].
- Scott, D., Gössling, S., Hall, C., Peeters, P. (2015), Can tourism be part of the decarbonized global economy? The costs and risks of alternate carbon reduction policy pathways. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 53, 1-21.
- Wang, J.Y.; Zhang, H. (2019). Tourism competitive potential and tourism competitiveness in the countries along the Belt and Road. *Qinghai Soc. Sci.*, 6, 62–68. [Google Scholar].
- Zhou, Q.L.; Zhan, B.M. (2017). A study of service trade cooperation potential between China and the countries of Belt and Road —Based on the international competitiveness of service industry. *West Forum*, 9, 111–124. [Google Scholar].
- Wang, S.J.; Xie, J.; Yue, Z.L.(2020). China's glacier tourism: Potential evaluation and spatial planning. *J. Destin. Mark. Manag.*, 18, 1–10. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef].